

DESIGNING A STUDY ON RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT, INNOVATION ACTIVITIES IN PRODUCTION COMPANIES IN THE POST- PANDEMIC REALITY

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Abstract

Purpose – analyzing the research - development - innovation activities carried out in the production companies in Bihor county and following the influence that the pandemic had on their deployment.

Methodology/approach - Designing a questionnaire-based marketing research.

Findings – it is important to analyze the research and development activities and identify some levers that lead to their improvement, starting from the research of the concrete situation in the post-pandemic industrial environment.

Research limitations/implications – the designed questionnaire will be applied until the end of 2022 and the research results will be obtained, processed and published later.

Practical implications – obtaining a realistic picture of research and development activities regarding the production companies in Bihor county.

Originality/value – the direct involvement of production companies by collecting data directly from the economic environment of production companies.

Key words: research, development, innovation.

Introduction

Human progress has been generated by research and development activities constantly carried out, consciously or spontaneously. Nowadays, technique and technology are evolving at an accelerated pace, and to meet this challenge companies must modernize, develop, be flexible, predictable and quickly adapt to market demands. Everything that means evolution and development in the company's activity, regardless of the form, level and way of manifestation, aims to: increase productivity, increase product quality, decrease costs, rapid circulation of information of any nature and form, etc. everything in compliance with the principles of sustainable development. These objectives can only be achieved through innovative processes whose complexity has become increasingly visible. Research and development activities also fall into the category of innovative processes in companies.

This has led to the organizational development of innovative activities in two directions: some companies have created in their composition organizational structures specialized in research, development, innovation, others carry out these activities according to the needs faced by the company at a certain moment or context making use of the means at their disposal.

During the two years of the covid 19 pandemic, but also after that, the research and development activities carried out in companies also underwent changes. These changes were reflected in: the way innovative activities are carried out, the adoption of improved work procedures both at the organizational level and within work groups, the digitization of some activities to facilitate or even stimulate research - development activities, flexibility and growth of the adaptability of the personnel involved in innovative activities, etc.

Conceptual boundaries imposed by legislation

The Romanian legislation¹ defines research and development activity as consisting of: scientific research, experimental development and innovation based on scientific research and experimental development. In turn, scientific research consists of fundamental research (it aims to obtain new knowledge about the fundamentals of observable phenomena and facts) and applied research (it involves original investigation carried out to acquire knowledge for a specific, practical objective)². Likewise, experimental development is defined as the activity that aims to obtain new materials, products, devices, processes, systems or services by capitalizing on the knowledge resulting from scientific research and/or the practical experience of those involved in the process.

Regarding innovation, this is the activity of implementing a new or improved product, service or process or a marketing method used in the practice of institutions or companies. As a result, innovation can be: product, process, marketing or organization oriented.

All these activities – scientific research, experimental development and innovation – are the main ones that generate knowledge as the basis of social and economic progress. The national research-development system is structured starting from them and is made up of all public and private law institutions as well as the units whose object is research-development. In this structure, in the category of private law units, are also included commercial companies whose object of activity is research - development or structures within them, legally constituted, an aspect that implies:

- the existence of a decision of the management of the company to set up the organizational structure for research and development
- its own name, its own organizational and operating regulations
- separate accounting in the company's global accounting
- its own staff and management.

Only under these legally regulated conditions, companies can be part of the national research-development system. At this moment, in Romania, the research, development and innovation (RDI) system consists of 263 public RDI organizations and about 600 enterprises³. In accordance with the membership of the national research and development system, companies can benefit from a series of fiscal facilities that refer to incentives granted to the calculation of the fiscal result in the following forms:

- an additional deduction, 50% of the eligible expenses for these activities, deduction used to establish the fiscal result;
- the application of the accelerated depreciation method for the apparatus and equipment intended for RDI activities
- exemption for the payment of income tax for natural persons, but for incomes of the nature of salaries and similar to them obtained for the conduct of research activities - applied development and experimental development defined by legislation; this regulation is important in the situation where companies carry out research - development activities and in associative forms.
- state aid for supporting research, development and innovation activities according to the state aid scheme regulated by the Order of the Minister of Research, Innovation and Digitization no. 20,827 from June 17, 2022

Also, depending on the development strategies of the RDI field at national and European level (digitalization, for example, which is defined as a strategic objective of European development starting from 2020) companies can benefit from public financial support through grants, subsidized loans and guarantees to loans for the innovative activities they carry out.

With all these facilities, many companies in the country carry out research - development - innovation activities that are not carried out in dedicated organizational structures. These activities can be carried

¹ Government Ordinance no. 57/2002 on scientific research and technological development approved with amendments by Law 324/2003 with subsequent amendments and additions, as well as the system of normative acts associated with the field of research - development - innovation

² Annex to Government Ordinance no. 57/2002 on scientific research and technological development

³ <https://www.research.gov.ro/ro/articol/4481/sistemul-national-de-cercetare>

out without the existence of a specialized organizational structure that has specialized employees, without its own organizational regulation and without distinct accounting and can be found at the level of any field of activity in the company. But, all these activities are aimed at obtaining improvements of some products and/or services, optimization of some processes that are necessary in the company, regardless of the fields of activity in which they take place.

Depending on the scale of the research-development projects to support these activities, the company needs suitable funding sources. These can come from:

- internal financing: from the company's own funds, capital contribution of shareholders (associates), etc.
- external financing of the company: funds from the state budget through various programs oriented towards research, development and innovation (RDI), from projects based on funds of the European Union (through the main Horizon Europe program oriented towards RDI) or of other international financial institutions, from credits, bank loans for different terms, financial and/or operational leasing, bond issuance, etc.

Regarding the funding from the state budget of the research and development activity, it is managed through several instruments: the National Plan for Research, Development and Innovation structured on several programs, sectoral plans, and other plans, programs and research projects which are launched to achieve certain objectives or which are intended for certain categories of researchers. All this is managed by the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization (which coordinates the National Research and Development System) together with the Ministry of Education and Research which, through the Executive Unit for the Financing of Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation (UEFISCDI), finances approximately 22 % of public funds allocated to research, development and innovation.

Definition of the study

In order to obtain a more comprehensive picture of the research and development activity within the companies in Bihor county, we will carry out a quantitative research by means of a survey based on a questionnaire. It is made up of topics that will analyze elements related to: the definition of the company, the types of research and development - innovation, research and development expenses - development and innovation, personnel involved and results) and contains 15 questions with closed and open answers. The scope of the research is represented by industrial companies from Bihor, regardless of their field of activity. The analyzed sample will consist of industrial production companies from the industrial parks of the city of Oradea as well as from other localities that have such companies: Alesd, Beiuș, Ștei, Marghita, etc. The questionnaire will be administered directly to company representatives, online or on-site. The collected data will then be centralized, processed and compared with national statistical data (obtained by the National Institute of Statistics through CD-BES and INOV statistical research) and European - results from the European innovation scoreboard (EIS) and from the Community Innovation Survey (CIS).

Following the centralization of the data of this study, it will be possible to create business models oriented towards innovation and the implementation of its results in all areas of the company's activity. The structure of the questionnaire is presented below. It should be noted that for its administration, we use a detailed form that contains a series of specifications that allow the unitary interpretation of the requested data.

The questionnaire is designed as follows:

1. Please specify the type of your company on Dec. 31. 2021:

A. Resident enterprise	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
B. Multinational company		
<i>B.1. controlled from Romania</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
<i>B.2. controlled from the outside</i>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>

2. What is the main activity of your company?
specify _____

2. In 2021, did your company carry out research and development activity within a research and development department or a research and development team?
 Yes No

3. Please specify what was the distribution of R&D expenses from the total research and development expenses in 2021, depending on the type of R&D

	% in total expenses R-D	of which: in the R-D department
Basic research		
Applied research		
Experimental development		

4. For 2021, what is the method of covering total R-D expenses depending on the source of funding

	Funding source	%
1	Întreprinderi cu activitate economică, din care:	
1.1	<i>company's own sources (microproduction/services, etc.)</i>	
1.2	<i>enterprises (units) belonging to the same group</i>	
1.3	<i>other enterprises (units)</i>	
2	Public funds	
3	Higher education units	
4	Private non-profit organizations	
5	From abroad, from which:	
5.1	<i>from the European Community</i>	
6	Other sources (including loans)	
	Total funding sources	100

5. What is the value of the ratio between the total R-D expenses and the total number of employees in your company? But the value of the ratio between total R-D expenses and the number of employees involved in research and development activities?

	Ratio lei/employee	out of which: in the department of R-D lei/employee
Ratio of total R-D expenses and total number of employees (full-time)		
Total R-D expenditure ratio and number of R-D employees (full-time)		

6. On December 31, 2021, what is the share of employees involved in research - development activities in the total number of employees of your company?
 Write the weight here _____

7. In 2021, what was the distribution of staff involved in research and development activities, by occupation, in full-time equivalent?

		No. full-time equivalent staff FTE*	From which: Female
1	Researchers		
1.1	out of which: internal staff		
2	Technicians and assimilated		
2.1	out of which: internal staff		
3	Other categories of staff		
3.1	put of which: internal staff		
4	Total number of people		
4.1	out of which: internal staff		

8. For the next 3 years, 2022 – 2025, do you intend to carry out research - development activities?

	Yes	No
Basic research		
Applied research		
Experimental development		

9. In 2021, did your company launch new or improved products (goods or services)?

	YES	NO
New on the market (Not previously offered by any of your competitors)		
New for the company (Identical or very similar to products already offered by your competitors)		

10. In 2021, for which of the following innovations in your company new products/services, business, marketing or organizational processes were created or existing ones were improved?

	Yes	No
Methods of producing or developing goods or providing services	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Logistics, delivery or distribution methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information processing or communication methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Accounting methods or other administrative operations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Business practices for organizing procedures or external relations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Methods of organizing workplace responsibility, decision-making or human resource management	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marketing methods for promotion, packaging, pricing, product placement or after-sales service*	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

11. Which of the following types of innovative research and development activities were carried out by your company in 2021?

	Yes	No
1. Internal research and development (R&D) activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If YES, in what way?		
1.1 <u>Continuously</u> <i>(the enterprise had its own permanent R-D staff)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1.2 <u>Occasionally</u> <i>(the enterprise had R-D staff only when needed)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. External research and development activities subcontracted to other enterprises (including enterprises of the same group) or with public or private research organizations	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>

12. What types of tax facilities have you obtained for carrying out research and development activities in 2021?

		Yes	No
1.	Incentives granted for the calculation of the fiscal result through the additional deduction (in the proportion of 50%) of the eligible expenses	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	Incentives granted for the calculation of the fiscal result by applying the accelerated depreciation method for apparatus and equipment intended for RDI activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	Exemption for the payment of income tax for natural persons but for incomes of the nature of salaries and similar to them obtained for the conduct of research activities - applied development and experimental development	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	Public financial support through grants, subsidized loans and loan guarantees		
4.1	Local or regional authorities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.2	Government	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.3	The EU program Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.4	Other financial support from EU institutions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	Other forms, list: _____		

13. In 2021, your company requested:

		YES	NO
1.	Registration and application for a <u>patent</u>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	Application for registration of an <u>industrial design</u>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	Application for registration of a <u>manufacturing mark</u>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	<u>Copyright</u> claim	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	Use of <u>trade secrets*</u> in product manufacturing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6.	Application for using a <u>utility model</u>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

14. In your company, do innovative activities take place outside the specialized research-development department?

Yes No

15. What types of innovations are carried out in your company?

		Yes	No
1.	Product innovations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	Process innovations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	Marketing innovations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	Organizational innovations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

16. Evaluate and/or estimate the completion mode of innovative activities that did not have the results listed in question 14

		Yes	No
1.	Innovative activities not completed in 2021 but <u>ongoing</u> by the end of 2022	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	Innovation activities <u>abandoned</u> in 2021	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	Innovation activities <u>suspended</u> in 2021 but with the potential to resume them in the following period	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	Innovation activities completed but not applied in 2021	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

17. Compared to the years before the covid 19 pandemic, how were research and development activities influenced?

		Yes	No
1.	Budgets for such activities have been cut	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	Research and development budgets have been increased	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	Work procedures have been modified to facilitate/stimulate research and development activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	Procedures were imposed to make the way of working (remote) more flexible for the staff involved in these activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	Digitization elements of these activities have been introduced	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6.	Other forms; list: _____		

18. Compared to the years before the covid 19 pandemic, how were the innovative activities carried out in the company, other than research and development, influenced?

		Yes	No
1.	Budgets for such activities have been cut	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	Budgets have been increased to stimulate innovation of all kinds	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	Work procedures have been modified to facilitate/stimulate innovative activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	Procedures were imposed to make the way of working (remote) more flexible for the staff involved in these activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	Digitization elements of these activities have been introduced	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6.	Other forms; list: _____		

19. In the following period, until the end of 2022, will you introduce operational, procedural, managerial, etc. measures for innovative, research and development activities that will lead to their stimulation and the legal registration of their results?

Yes No

Conclusions

In an economic environment with accelerated dynamics and in the conditions of the emergence of disruptive factors with major effects, as in recent years the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine have been, it is essential that companies adapt to face these challenges .

Whether it is integrated into the production activity, or a separate structure is created with a name and function adapted to the specific needs of the firm, research, development and innovation are gaining importance.

Research-development and innovation activity in companies must be boosted, a fact also provided for by European directives, in this sense a closer collaboration between research institutions, universities and companies is necessary, as the main element of generating added value in society.

The present work represents a first stage of a larger study regarding the research, development, innovation activities carried out in the companies of Bihor county in the post-pandemic reality. This will be continued by applying the designed questionnaire, centralizing and processing the data, establishing the existing results at the time of application and determining practical ways to stimulate these types of activities. The proposals will be sent to the companies participating in the study to be analyzed and possibly applied.

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